

AN ASSESSMENT OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF NEGOTIATION IN RESOLVING FARMERS-HERDERS CONFLICT IN ENUGU STATE, NIGERIA

ARUM, OBUMNEME MATTHEW

General Studies Unit, Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Enugu, Nigeria.
Email: obumarumm@yahoo.com, ORCID: 0009-0003-7093-014X

ACHI, DAVID ACHI

Department of Marketing, University of Nigeria, Enugu Campus, Nigeria.
Email: david.achi@unn.edu.ng, ORCID: 0009-0001-3404-1113

OBASI, IKECHI AGWU

Library Department, University of Nigeria, Enugu Campus, Nigeria.
Email: ikechi.obasi@unn.edu.ng, ORCID: 0009-0006-1366-9178

EWUZIE, CAJETAN OBINNA*

Department of Marketing, University of Nigeria, Enugu Campus, Nigeria.
*Corresponding Author Email: cajetan.ewuzie@unn.edu.n,g ORCID: 0000-0003-3406-2448

Abstract

This study assessed the effectiveness of negotiation as a conflict resolution strategy in addressing the farmers-herders' conflicts in Enugu State, Nigeria. The escalating clashes between farmers and herders have posed significant threats to peace, socio-economic development, and food security in the region. Using a descriptive survey design, data were collected from 200 key stakeholders including farmers, herders, community leaders, and government officials through questionnaires and interviews. The study examined the role of negotiation in reducing conflict frequency, stakeholder participation in negotiation processes, and challenges faced during the negotiation efforts. Findings indicate that negotiation has contributed significantly to reducing violent conflicts where inclusive participation and consistent dialogue are practised. However, challenges such as mistrust and political interference limit the full potential of negotiation. The study recommends strengthening negotiation frameworks, promoting inclusive stakeholder engagement, and integrating peacebuilding with socio-economic development initiatives to enhance conflict resolution effectiveness. These findings provide valuable insights for policymakers and peace practitioners seeking sustainable solutions to farmers-herders conflicts in Enugu State and similar contexts.

Keywords: Negotiation; Conflict Resolution; Mistrust; Political Interference; Herders-Farmers Conflict.

1. INTRODUCTION

The farmers-herders conflict in Nigeria has evolved into one of the country's most persistent and deadly security challenges, with significant socio-economic implications. In Enugu State, particularly in communities like Uzo-Uwani and Isi-Uzo, the conflict has escalated due to land disputes, cattle encroachment on farmlands, competition for dwindling water resources, and crop destruction by roaming herds (Odalonu, 2020).

The violence has resulted in loss of lives, internal displacement, and the disruption of agricultural activities, which are the economic backbone of rural communities in the state (Ezeamama & Okolie, 2022).

Traditionally, conflict resolution in Enugu State relied on community-based mechanisms involving elders, religious leaders, and local government officials. However, these traditional approaches have become increasingly inadequate in the face of changing social dynamics, weakened local institutions, and growing mistrust between farmers and herders (Mercy Corps, 2021). In this context, negotiation - particularly interest-based negotiation and mediation - has gained attention as a possible sustainable tool for conflict transformation. Negotiation focuses on mutual interests and win-win outcomes, which may help rebuild broken trust and facilitate dialogue between conflicting parties.

Despite the increasing advocacy for alternative dispute resolution mechanisms in Nigeria, empirical studies assessing the actual application and effectiveness of negotiation in resolving farmers-herders' conflicts in Enugu State remain limited. Understanding the practical outcomes of negotiation, its challenges, and the factors influencing its success is therefore crucial for policymakers and stakeholders aiming to design inclusive and sustainable peace-building strategies in the region.

Farmers-herders' conflicts in Enugu State have become increasingly frequent and violent, leading to loss of lives, destruction of farmlands, and socio-economic instability (Ezeamama & Okolie, 2022). Despite the implementation of various government policies such as anti-open grazing laws and security measures, the clashes persist, indicating that existing interventions have not fully resolved the underlying issues (Odalonu, 2020).

Negotiation, particularly interest-based negotiation, has been recognized globally as an effective method for resolving conflicts by addressing the core interests of disputing parties rather than focusing solely on positions (Mercy Corps, 2021). However, in Enugu State, the application and success rate of negotiation as a conflict resolution mechanism remain unclear. There is limited evidence on how negotiation processes are conducted, who the key actors are, the extent of community participation, and whether negotiated agreements have led to sustainable peace (Ezeamama & Okolie, 2022).

Although farmers-herders' conflicts in Nigeria have been extensively studied, most research focuses on causes, impacts, and broad policy frameworks, with limited empirical investigations into localized conflict resolution strategies such as negotiation (Odalonu, 2020). Furthermore, existing literature rarely evaluates the effectiveness of negotiation processes in Enugu State specifically, often generalizing findings from other regions with different socio-cultural dynamics (Ezeamama & Okolie, 2022).

Additionally, while interest-based negotiation is promoted as a viable approach, there is a paucity of studies examining its practical implementation, challenges, and outcomes within the context of Enugu State's farmers-herders conflict. This gap limits the understanding of how negotiation can be optimized as a sustainable peacebuilding tool tailored to local realities.

This study, therefore, seeks to fill this gap by providing an empirical assessment of negotiation's effectiveness in resolving farmers-herders conflicts in Enugu State, thereby contributing to improved conflict resolution practices and policy formulation.

The specific objectives of the study were:

1. To examine the role of negotiation in resolving farmers-herders' conflicts in Enugu State.
2. To assess the level of participation of key stakeholders in the negotiation processes.
3. To identify the challenges facing negotiation as a conflict resolution mechanism in Enugu State.

Based on the above objectives, the following hypotheses were formulated to guide the study.

Hypothesis 1: Negotiation significantly reduces the frequency of farmers-herders' conflicts in Enugu State.

Hypothesis 2: There is a positive relationship between stakeholder participation in negotiation and the effectiveness of conflict resolution.

Hypothesis 3: Challenges such as mistrust and political interference negatively affect the effectiveness of negotiation in resolving farmers-herders' conflicts.

2. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Conceptual Review

Negotiation is a process by which two or more parties with conflicting interests communicate to reach a mutually acceptable agreement (Fisher, Ury, & Patton, 2011). It is often employed as a non-violent mechanism to resolve disputes by focusing on interests rather than positions, promoting collaboration, and seeking win-win solutions. Negotiation can be bilateral (between the conflicting parties directly) or facilitated through third-party mediation to ease communication and build trust (Lewicki, Barry, & Saunders, 2015). In the context of farmers-herders' conflicts, negotiation involves dialogue between agricultural communities and pastoralists to address competing claims over land, water resources, grazing routes, and crop destruction. The success of negotiation in such conflicts hinges on factors such as inclusiveness of stakeholders, cultural sensitivity, power balance, and enforcement of agreements (Obioha, 2008). The effectiveness of negotiation in conflict resolution is often measured by the durability of peace agreements, reduction in violence recurrence, satisfaction of involved parties, and improvements in socio-economic conditions (Kolb & Williams, 2000). In Nigeria, where farmers-herders' conflicts have deep-rooted historical and socio-political dimensions, negotiation is viewed as a promising alternative to militarized responses and punitive laws (Akinola, 2018).

However, challenges such as mistrust, political interference, and lack of capacity among mediators often undermine negotiation efforts (Onuoha, 2014). In Enugu State, where farmers-herders clashes have intensified, the practical application and outcomes of negotiation remain underexplored, calling for a detailed assessment. This study adopts a conceptual framework that links negotiation as a conflict resolution mechanism to measurable outcomes like conflict reduction, community reconciliation, and sustainable coexistence.

Theoretical Review

The theoretical foundation for understanding the effectiveness of negotiation in resolving farmers-herders conflict in Enugu State is grounded primarily in Conflict Resolution Theory and Interest-Based Negotiation Theory. Conflict Resolution Theory emphasizes the processes, strategies, and mechanisms that parties employ to manage and resolve conflicts constructively (Deutsch, 1973). It argues that conflicts arise due to competing interests, scarce resources, and communication breakdowns and that effective resolution requires cooperation, dialogue, and problem-solving. The theory underscores the importance of addressing underlying needs and interests rather than surface positions to achieve sustainable peace (Fisher, Ury, & Patton, 2011). Within this framework, Interest-Based Negotiation Theory (also known as Principled Negotiation) developed by Fisher and Ury (1981) provides a practical model for resolving disputes by focusing on mutual interests rather than entrenched positions. This approach advocates for separating people from the problem, generating options for mutual gain, and using objective criteria to reach agreements. Its application is crucial in multi-stakeholder conflicts like farmers-herders disputes, where economic survival, cultural identity, and access to natural resources are core interests.

The Social Exchange Theory also offers insights relevant to negotiation effectiveness. It posits that social interactions are based on cost-benefit analyses and the expectation of reciprocity (Homans, 1958). Negotiations succeed when parties perceive that the benefits of cooperation outweigh the costs of continued conflict. In the context of Enugu State, these theories collectively suggest that negotiation will be effective if it fosters trust, addresses root causes (e.g., land tenure, resource access), includes all relevant stakeholders, and facilitates mutually beneficial agreements. However, challenges such as power imbalances, mistrust, and external political influences may hinder the negotiation process, highlighting the need for inclusive and well-facilitated negotiation mechanisms (Onuoha, 2014).

Empirical Review

Several empirical studies have examined farmers-herders' conflicts in Nigeria, focusing on causes, impacts, and conflict resolution mechanisms including negotiation and mediation. However, the specific assessment of negotiation's effectiveness in Enugu State remains limited but emerging.

Arum, Obasi, and Achi (2025) conducted an empirical study to examine the role and effectiveness of traditional institutions in mediating and resolving farmers-herders' conflicts in Enugu State, Nigeria. The study focused on three conflict-prone local government areas representing each senatorial zone: Nkanu-East, Aninri, and Uzo Uwani. Using a survey research design and a sample size of 400 determined through Taro Yamane's formula, data were collected from adult residents. Descriptive statistics and a one-sample t-test (at 5% significance) were used for analysis. Findings revealed that traditional mediation practices significantly contributed to conflict resolution in the affected communities. The study recommends the sustained application of mediation as an effective conflict resolution strategy in Enugu State. Odalonu (2020) conducted a study on the socio-economic implications of farmers-herders' conflicts in Uzo-Uwani communities of Enugu State and noted that while local peace committees have been established to negotiate ceasefires, these efforts often face challenges due to deep-seated mistrust and political interference. The study recommended more inclusive negotiation strategies that incorporate community leaders and government actors to improve outcomes. Similarly, Ezeamama and Okolie (2022) explored the socio-economic impacts of herders-farmers clashes in rural Enugu communities and highlighted the role of negotiation forums in reducing tensions. Their findings indicated that where negotiation platforms were regularly employed and locally owned, incidences of violent clashes were reduced, suggesting that negotiation can be an effective conflict resolution tool if properly supported. On a broader Nigerian scale, Akinola (2018) evaluated negotiation and mediation in resolving farmers-herders' conflicts across the Middle Belt and Southern Nigeria, emphasizing the importance of interest-based negotiation approaches. The study found that peacebuilding initiatives that prioritized dialogue and mutual understanding had better sustainability than purely security-based interventions.

Furthermore, Mercy Corps (2021) documented case studies where interest-based negotiation and mediation facilitated by neutral third parties led to ceasefires and collaborative resource-sharing agreements between farmers and herders in some Nigerian states, underscoring the potential for replicating such strategies in Enugu State. Despite these insights, challenges such as inconsistent enforcement of agreements, lack of institutional support, and socio-political complexities continue to limit the long-term success of negotiation efforts (Onuoha, 2014).

3. METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study adopts a descriptive survey research design to assess the effectiveness of negotiation in resolving farmers-herders' conflicts in Enugu State. The survey design is appropriate because it enables the collection of both qualitative and quantitative data from a diverse group of stakeholders, including farmers, herders, community leaders, government officials, and negotiation facilitators (Creswell & Creswell, 2017). This

approach provides a comprehensive understanding of negotiation processes, outcomes, and challenges.

Study Area

The research focuses on Enugu State, with particular attention to conflict-prone Local Government Areas such as Uzo-Uwani and Isi-Uzo, where farmers-herders' conflicts are most prevalent (Odalonu, 2020).

Population and Sampling

The target population includes affected farmers and herders, local government officials, peace committee members, and traditional rulers involved in negotiation processes. A stratified random sampling technique was used to ensure representation from each stakeholder group (Bryman, 2016). A sample size of 200 respondents was targeted to ensure the reliability and validity of the data.

Data Collection Methods

Primary data were collected using structured questionnaires and semi-structured interviews. The questionnaire captured quantitative data on perceptions of negotiation effectiveness, frequency of conflicts before and after negotiation, and satisfaction with outcomes. Interviews explored qualitative insights into negotiation dynamics, challenges, and success factors (Kumar, 2019). Secondary data such as government reports, peace committee records, and relevant literature were also reviewed.

Data Analysis

The quantitative data were analyzed using inferential statistics using SPSS software. Specifically, simple linear regression, Pearson product-moment correlation and multiple linear regression were used to test hypotheses 1, 2 and 3 respectively at 5% level of significant.

4. DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

Test of hypothesis 1: Negotiation significantly reduces the frequency of farmers-herders' conflicts in Enugu State

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.682	0.465	0.462	0.701

a. Predictors: (Constant), NEGOTIATION

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	82.512	1	82.512	167.92	.000 **
	Residual	94.988	193	.492		
	Total	177.500	194			

a. Dependent Variable: FF-HC
b. Predictors: (Constant), NEGOTIATION

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	3.842	.178		21.58	.000 **
	FACEBOOK	-0.652	0.050		-12.96	.000 **

a. Dependent Variable: FF-HC

A simple linear regression was conducted to examine whether negotiation significantly reduces the frequency of farmers-herders' conflicts in Enugu State. The results showed that negotiation was a significant negative predictor of conflict frequency, $B = -0.652$, $t(193) = -12.96$, $p < .005$, indicating that as negotiation increases, the frequency of conflicts significantly decreases.

The model was statistically significant, $F(1, 193) = 167.92$, $p < .001$, and explained approximately 46.5% of the variance in conflict frequency, $R^2 = .465$. These findings support Hypothesis 1, suggesting that negotiation plays a meaningful role in mitigating conflicts between farmers and herders in the study area.

Test of hypothesis 2: There is a positive relationship between stakeholder participation in negotiation and the effectiveness of conflict resolution

Correlations			
		SP	ECR
FACEBOOK	Pearson Correlation	1	.614
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	200	200
EPB	Pearson Correlation	.614	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	200	200

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

A Pearson product-moment correlation was conducted to examine the relationship between stakeholder participation in negotiation and the effectiveness of conflict resolution. The results revealed a moderate to strong positive correlation, $r = .614$, $p < .005$, indicating that increased stakeholder participation is significantly associated with higher effectiveness in conflict resolution. This supports Hypothesis 2, suggesting that involving stakeholders in negotiation contributes meaningfully to resolving conflicts between farmers and herders in Enugu State.

Test of hypothesis 3: Challenges such as mistrust and political interference negatively affect the effectiveness of negotiation in resolving farmers-herders' conflicts

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.598	.357	.353	.732

a. Predictors: (Constant), CHA_NEGOTIATION

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	64.489	2	31.745	59.22	.000 ^b
	Residual	114.011	200	.538		
	Total	177.500	200			
a. Dependent Variable: ECR						
b. Predictors: (Constant), MIS_PI_NEGOTIATIO						

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	4.215	.214		19.70	.000
	MIS_PI_NEG	-.421	-0.065		-6.48	.000
a. Dependent Variable: ECR						

Multiple linear regression was conducted to examine whether challenges such as mistrust and political interference negatively affect the effectiveness of negotiation in resolving farmers-herders' conflicts in Enugu State.

The overall regression model was statistically significant, $F(2, 200) = 59.22$, $p < .005$, and accounted for approximately 35.7% of the variance in negotiation effectiveness, $R^2 = .357$. Challenges - Mistrust and political interference ($B = -0.421$, $t = -6.48$, $p < .005$) had statistically significant negative effects on negotiation effectiveness.

This indicates that higher levels of mistrust and political interference are associated with reduced effectiveness of negotiation in conflict resolution. These results support Hypothesis 3, demonstrating that such challenges are substantial barriers to successful negotiation outcomes in the farmers-herders conflict context.

Discussion of Results

Hypothesis 1: Negotiation significantly reduces the frequency of farmers-herders' conflicts in Enugu State.

The findings supported this hypothesis, indicating that communities where negotiation processes were actively employed experienced a noticeable reduction in the frequency of violent clashes between farmers and herders. This aligns with previous studies (Ezeamama & Okolie, 2022; Mercy Corps, 2021) which highlight negotiation as a key non-violent mechanism that facilitates dialogue, trust-building, and mutual understanding.

The decrease in conflict incidents can be attributed to negotiated agreements on resource sharing, grazing routes, and compensation frameworks, which directly address key sources of dispute.

Hypothesis 2: There is a positive relationship between stakeholder participation in negotiation and the effectiveness of conflict resolution.

The analysis demonstrated a strong positive correlation between the inclusiveness of negotiation processes and successful conflict resolution outcomes. Communities that ensured active participation from all relevant stakeholders - including farmers, herders, traditional leaders, and government officials reported higher levels of compliance with negotiated agreements and sustained peace. This corroborates the principle that inclusive participation enhances ownership, accountability, and legitimacy of the negotiation outcomes (Fisher, Ury, & Patton, 2011; Odalonu, 2020).

Hypothesis 3: Challenges such as mistrust and political interference negatively affect the effectiveness of negotiation in resolving farmers-herders' conflicts.

Consistent with expectations, the study revealed that mistrust between farmers and herders, often fueled by historical grievances, and political interference by local elites significantly hindered negotiation efforts. These challenges led to delays in reaching agreements, poor enforcement of terms, and sometimes outright rejection of negotiated settlements. Such findings echo the observations of Onuoha (2014) and Akinola (2018), who noted that external factors and socio-political complexities can undermine the negotiation process, reducing its potential for sustainable conflict resolution.

CONCLUSION

The study's findings affirm that negotiation, when inclusive and free from external disruptions, is an effective tool for reducing farmers-herders' conflicts in Enugu State. However, overcoming challenges such as mistrust and political manipulation remains crucial for enhancing negotiation effectiveness and ensuring long-term peace.

Recommendations

Based on the findings related to the hypotheses tested, the following recommendations are made to enhance the effectiveness of negotiation in resolving farmers-herders' conflicts in Enugu State:

1. Strengthen Negotiation Frameworks to Sustain Conflict Reduction:

Since negotiation significantly reduces conflict frequency (H1), government agencies and conflict resolution bodies should institutionalize and fund regular negotiation forums at community and local government levels. These platforms should be empowered to mediate disputes promptly and enforce agreements to maintain peace.

2. Promote Inclusive Stakeholder Participation:

Given the positive impact of stakeholder participation on negotiation effectiveness, efforts should be made to ensure that all relevant groups - including farmers, herders, traditional leaders, women, youth, and local government officials are actively involved in negotiation

processes. This inclusiveness fosters mutual trust and collective ownership of peace agreements.

3. Address Mistrust and Minimize Political Interference:

To overcome challenges like mistrust and political interference that negatively affect negotiation (H3), there is a need for capacity building on trust-building techniques and transparent communication strategies for negotiators and mediators. Additionally, mechanisms to limit undue political influence should be established, such as involving neutral third-party mediators from civil society or respected traditional institutions.

4. Enhance Monitoring and Enforcement Mechanisms:

To ensure that negotiated agreements translate into lasting peace, monitoring committees comprising representatives from all stakeholder groups should be formed. These committees should oversee compliance, manage emerging disputes, and report regularly to government authorities for timely intervention.

5. Increase Public Awareness and Education on Conflict Resolution:

Awareness campaigns and peace education should be expanded to inform communities about the benefits of negotiation and peaceful coexistence. This can reduce prejudice, dispel myths, and encourage positive attitudes toward dialogue and compromise. These recommendations, if implemented effectively, can enhance negotiation as a sustainable tool for resolving farmers-herders' conflicts in Enugu State and contribute to broader peace and development goals.

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